

Development and validation of a portable adiabatic calorimeter based on cost-effective components

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Abstract. Adiabatic calorimetry is a widely recognised characterisation method that involves casting the studied material in a thermally isolated vessel, ensuring no energy exchange, and achieving so-called adiabatic conditions. This isolation enables the conduct of cement hydration without heat loss, ensuring consistent material characterisation independent of environmental conditions. Rigorous testing and validation were conducted to ensure compliance with the EN12390-15 standard for adiabatic calorimetry in concrete. Furthermore, a comparative analysis with a commercial adiabatic calorimeter demonstrated the reliability and accuracy of the proposed device in the characterization of mortar. This innovative device not only addresses the challenges of achieving adiabatic conditions in material characterisation but also provides a cost-effective and adaptable solution that can significantly benefit laboratories and industries engaged in research and development within the field.

Introduction

Adiabatic calorimetry can be defined as the study of heat generation/absorption by an ongoing chemical reaction in absence of heat exchange with the environment, meaning that the reaction takes place completely independently from the environment. This is particularly interesting for the study of cement hydration and the temperature prediction of mass concrete during hydration [1,2].

To attain adiabatic conditions, the vessel where the material is cast is immersed in a water bath whose temperature is controlled and continuously equalised with the temperature inside the vessel. In order to enhance the proposed device's accessibility in laboratory settings, its development was conducted around cost-effective components and open-source resources, with a microcontroller, Arduino Mega, as the brain of the operations. This strategic choice not only promotes widespread adoption but also endows the device with scalability and flexibility.

The proposed device aims to enable in-situ quality control of the heat signature of a given mix and study the binder consistency in chemical terms on a construction site. This type of device is not yet available to the industry and promises an improved quality control process as well as more sustainable constructions.

Validation of the proposed device

According to standard EN12390-15 [3], different requirements are necessary to qualify a device of adiabatic, more specifically the adiabaticism error criteria, that should be less than 0.05K/h. To comply with this requirement, the validation process was composed of several phases; in the first phase, the aim was to ensure the correct capabilities of the system to reach

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an arbitrary temperature comprised between 20°C and 70°C, which are the expected temperatures for regular masonry mortars hydration and maintain it with an average temperature comprised between target and target minus 0.05°C. This phase allowed the refinement of the temperature control algorithm's parameters.

Once the first phase was completed, the second phase consisted of testing the device with material to validate the device's correct behaviour with a dynamic target. To this date, this phase is still under work. A graph obtained with the proposed device is shown in Figure 1. The average temperature difference between the water bath and the mortar is 0.006°C, confirming the right setting of the algorithm parameters. However, the focus needs to be on the phase after the heat generation reaches a plateau to ensure compliance with the adiabatic error requirements.

Fig. 1. Hydration of mortar with proposed device

After completing this second phase, the final validation phase will compare the proposed device with a standard adiabatic calorimeter.

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